

Effect of dispersive and relativistic optical model potentials on the production cross-section calculation of ^{225}Ac from ^{232}Th using proton energy

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Abstract

Targeted Alpha Therapy (TAT) is considered the best method of treatment of malignant tissues. Alpha particles have interesting properties of destroying the cancerous cells due to their short penetration and high linear energy transfer. Hence, the use of alpha emitting radionuclides allows for targeting specific cancerous cells and killing of the individual cells while minimizing the toxicity to the surrounding healthy cells. The sources of the alpha for such application are the major concern. Investigation shows that Actinium-225 and Bismuth-213 are potential candidates for the production of alpha for TAT. Because of its short half-life, the best method of production of Bismuth-213 is through $^{225}\text{Ac}/^{213}\text{Bi}$ generator hence the study of the production of Actinium-225. Critical literature review reveals that proton bombardment of thorium-232 is the best method of producing Actinium-225. Therefore, the theoretical calculations of the production cross-sections were conducted using a nuclear modular code Empire. The calculated cross-sections were compared with one another and with the measured production cross-sections obtained from the experimental nuclear reaction data exchange format library contained in the nuclear data section of the International Atomic Energy Agency (IAEA), to investigate the effect of optical model's configurations and the effect of the dispersive and relativistic optical model potentials on the production cross-section. The optical models' configurations were designated by D1, D2 and D3 respectively for models that used to calculate coupled-channel transmission coefficients for the incident channel in addition to Distorted-Wave Born Approximation uncoupled, used for coupled-channel transmission coefficients for the incident and outgoing channel in addition to Distorted-Wave Born Approximation uncoupled, and used for Distorted-Wave Born Approximation calculation for all collective levels. The potentials are dispersive and relative potential, non-dispersive and relative potential, and the non-dispersive and non-relativistic potentials. The result obtained shows that the optical model configuration used to calculate coupled-channel transmission coefficients for the incident channel in addition to Distorted-Wave Born Approximation uncoupled produces the better effect on the production cross-section. Similarly, the model with Non-Dispersive and Non-Relativistic potentials produces netter yield while the optical model with Dispersive and Relativistic potential is more physically conservative. Hence any of the optical models can be used for the calculation of the production cross-section, regardless of the dispersive and relativistic potentials of the optical model.

Keywords

Coupled-Channel, Dispersive, Distorted-Wave Born Approximation, Empire, Relativistic, Targeted Alpha Therapy

Introduction

The development of alpha emitting radiopharmaceuticals for Targeted Alpha Therapy (TAT) is an active area of academic and commercial research worldwide owing to the properties of alpha suitable for the purpose (Shaunak and Ashley 2018; Francisco et al. 2020). This includes the penetration range and the linear energy transfer which are critical factors of the radiopharmaceutical radiation, as the potent pathway of malignant cell destruction is related to the direct interaction between ionization events and the deoxyribonucleic acid string in the nucleus. The emitted alpha particles possess a suitable penetration range such that the neighbouring healthy cells are not affected (Bryce et al. 2021).

The International Atomic Energy Agency (IAEA) has supported series of investigations to identify and quantify the production routes and decay characteristics of such radioisotopes that have existing and emerging importance in nuclear medicine (Nichols 2013). Several candidate isotopes for TAT are currently under clinical and preclinical evaluation, including ^{225}Ac and ^{213}Bi . ^{213}Bi ($t_{1/2} = 45.6$ min) decays by one alpha and two beta particles to a stable ^{209}Bi . The alpha energy is 8.4 MeV (Kellerbauer et al. 2020). ^{225}Ac ($t_{1/2} = 9.9$ days) decays to stable ^{209}Bi via four alpha- and two beta-decays. It is used as a generator of ^{213}Bi . Because of the short half-life of ^{213}Bi , $^{225}\text{Ac}/^{213}\text{Bi}$ generator is considered as the best method its production for TAT applications (McDevitt et al. 1999a, 1999b; Deborah et al. 2005; Rose et al. 2005; Melville et al. 2006; Longmena et al. 2023). This method of radionuclide production has a significant benefit by allowing for rapid generation of short-lived radionuclide on site for patient-specific treatments when needed. The few alpha emission by the ^{213}Bi contributes to lower overall systemic toxicity and off-target effects in the patient. The much shorter half-life of 45.6 minutes means it decays faster, resulting in a shorter overall radiation exposure period for patients and healthcare providers. With these advantages, several clinical trials have demonstrated the potentials of ^{213}Bi and ^{225}Ac radiopharmaceuticals to treat advanced cancers (Ermolaev et al. 2012; Tapas and Pillai 2013; Shaunak and Ashley 2018; Francisco et al. 2020; Randy et al. 2020; Ahenkorah et al. 2021; Bryce et al. 2021). The development of the drugs faces limited supply due to shortage of the production facilities among other challenges that have slowed the progress of the application. These resulted to high cost that makes ^{225}Ac inaccessible to many researchers.

The present reliable supply of ^{225}Ac comes entirely from the existing ^{229}Th -based generator systems in the United States, Germany, and Russia in a total quantity not much to reach the world demand (Engle 2018; Robertson et al. 2018). These sources are relying on the build-up of ^{229}Th through the decay of ^{233}U stockpiles produced between 1954 and 1970. Most of the alternative production methods explored involved the use of ^{226}Ra as a target material. The $^{226}\text{Ra}(p,2n)^{225}\text{Ac}$ is the only favorable reaction

for the production of ^{225}Ac on accelerator but it faces challenges of the danger of handling ^{226}Ra , the target material, because it is radioactive. It is restricted and extremely dangerous at irradiation, chemical processing and target material recovery (Ermolaev et al. 2012). Due to these challenges of handling large quantity of ^{226}Ra and the low yield of ^{229}Th , the spallation reactions on naturally occurring ^{232}Th and ^{238}U were the only other alternatives (Engle 2018; Robertson et al. 2018). ^{232}Th has a lot of advantages over ^{226}Ra . It is the preferred chemical form for post-irradiation processing of the target and it is highly available in stockpile in a number of countries and more can be produced in large quantities from the oxide or the nitrate (Andrew et al. 2018). This availability means that recycling of irradiated ^{232}Th target material may not be necessary. It is not prohibitively radioactive and poses fewer radiological hazards. Another advantage of this method is that facilities already exist with demonstrated ability to perform target fabrication, irradiation, and processing. Isolation of ^{225}Ac from irradiated thorium metal has been demonstrated by both American and Russian research groups (Andrew et al. 2018).

While spallation of naturally occurring ^{238}U will also produce ^{225}Ac , ^{232}Th irradiation is preferred for a number of reasons. The $^{238}\text{U}(p,x)^{225}\text{Ac}$ reaction cross-section is about 10 times lower (as modelled using FLUKA and GEANT4), and due to the higher density and lower melting point of uranium, thorium targets could more safely handle the higher heat load induced by higher beam currents (Robertson et al. 2018). The coproduction of fissile ^{239}Pu and ^{235}U is also avoided by ^{232}Th irradiation. The challenge with this method is that only a few existing accelerators can produce proton beams with a current and energy sufficient for large-scale ^{225}Ac production. So, there is need for intense study of the reaction mechanism of the production of ^{225}Ac from spallation reaction of ^{232}Th with proton projectile. Though the direct medical application of ^{225}Ac produced by this method is problematic because the restrictions for the long-lived impurity ^{227}Ac may be very strong (Ermolaev et al. 2012). However, ^{225}Ac obtained by the method is prospective for preparation of a $^{225}\text{Ac}/^{213}\text{Bi}$ isotope generator (Zhuikov et al. 2011). The modelling of the production routes of ^{225}Ac through thorium bombardment with proton beam ($^{232}\text{Th}(p,x)^{225}\text{Ac}$) are being investigated using different theoretical models. Weidner et al. (2012) in comparison of the theoretical predictions with their experimental data had reasonable-to-good agreement by different theoretical codes (ALICE2010, Bertini+MPM+Dresner+RAL event-generator, and Liege intra-nuclear cascade model INCL). Zhuikov et al. (2011) in the production of ^{225}Ac reported that their experimental data lie between the theoretical data calculated by ALICE-IPPE and cascade evaporation (CEF). Ermolaev et al. (2012) used ALICE and CEF calculations also.

Even though some of these codes such as Talys are robust, Empire has advantage of specialized heavy ion and high-energy performance, flexibility in nuclear level

density models, data evaluation pedigree, and advanced fission channel treatment (Herman et al. 2005). Extensive theoretical study of the nuclear reaction is very important for the understanding and guided design for effective and successful improvement on the production process. Studies of excitation functions of charged particle induced reactions are of considerable significance for testing nuclear models as well as for practical applications, especially in accelerators production of radioisotopes. The production of non-conventional radionuclides, however, demands detailed nuclear data work covering both experimental investigations and nuclear model calculations. In this study, the production cross-section of ^{225}Ac through proton bombardment of Thorium-232 is calculated using a nuclear model code Empire (Herman et al. 2015). The calculation was done with the emphasis on optical models and the optical model potentials.

The purpose of the study is to ascertain the effect of the dispersion and relativistic optical model potentials on the production cross-section of ^{225}Ac from ^{232}Th by proton energy. The result of the research will provide strong information to researchers on the choice of models in production of ^{225}Ac , hence the production of ^{213}Bi . The theory of nuclear reaction in relation to dispersity and the relativity of the optical model is discussed in the section of theory of the calculation. The result obtained are compared graphically with the experimental data from nuclear data library. The result and the discussion are presented thereafter as well as the conclusion.

Theory of the calculation

Nuclear reaction is a collision between nucleon or nucleus and another nucleon or nucleus. This reaction is marked by the entry channel of the reactants and the exit channel of the reaction products. The complete description of the reaction includes the relative energy of the incoming nuclei and the outgoing nuclei, polarization and/or excitation energies for spin and excited nuclei and the scattering angle of the outgoing products. In practice three types of models, optical model, the pre-equilibrium model and the compound nucleus model linked together, as illustrated by Hilaire (2014) shown in Fig. 1, are required to completely describe nuclear reaction.

Figure 1. Sequence of nuclear models required to describe a nuclear reaction (Hilaire 2014).

All these models need to be implemented in a nuclear reaction code aiming at producing useful information. It can be observed in Fig. 1, that in addition to the output (elastic, fission or inelastic data), the optical model also provides the other models with an input such as the reaction cross-section (σ_{Reaction}) to the pre-equilibrium model and transmission coefficient (T_{ij}) to the compound nucleus. This shows how important the optical model is in the description of nuclear reaction. It determines the reaction cross-section that the pre-equilibrium and compound nucleus models are then going to spread in the different outgoing open channels. It also provides the direct (or shape) elastic and total cross-sections, as well as the elastic angular distributions.

The information obtained from the cross-section depends strongly on the internal structure of the initial and final nuclei in relation to the energy of the nuclei involve. Generally, the interaction can be scattering interaction where the path of the incoming nucleon/nucleus is deviated by the target nucleon/nucleus. The scattering can be direct (Shape) elastic where the two nuclei properties remain the same before and after the reaction or inelastic where there is exchange of energy between the nuclei during the scattering. In both scattering interaction, there is no loss of the initial flux. There is probability also of the absorption of part of the incoming flux by the scattering potential. In classical physics this is described by introducing an imaginary reflection coefficient which accounts for the absorption. In nuclear scattering, this is achieved by introducing a complex scattering potential known as the optical model potential. Generally, the optical model potential contains a Coulomb and a nuclear part. The Coulomb part is usually taken as a potential of the uniformly charged sphere. The nuclear part contains volume, surface, and spin-orbit parts. Each of these consists of real and imaginary component so that the full potential reads:

$$U_{opt} = +V_c(r) \text{ a Coulomb term}$$

$$-Vf_v(r) \text{ a real volume term}$$

$$+V_s g_v(r) \text{ a real surface term}$$

$$-iW_s g_w(r) \text{ an imaginary surface term}$$

$$-iW_v f_w(r) \text{ an imaginary volume term}$$

$$-d_{so}l \cdot sV_{so} h v_{so}(r) \text{ a real spin-orbit term}$$

$$+i d_{so}l \cdot sW_{so} h v_{so}(r) \text{ and an imaginary spin-orbit term} \quad 1$$

where V and W are potential depths.

The fundamental theoretical tool that provides the basis of nuclear reaction data analysis and evaluations is the optical model. The optical model potential parameters reproduce well nuclear reaction cross-section data over a wide energy range. For scattering of point particles, only elastic scattering takes place, which can be described

by the Schrödinger equation for a two-body system with some potential between the colliding particles. The Schrödinger equation provide a direct and simple form of optical potential based on the impulse of approximation. The optical potential $U_{opt}(\mathbf{r})$ from the Schrödinger equation is taken as follows (Carlson 2000).

$$\left[\frac{\hbar^2}{2\mu} \nabla^2 + U_{opt}(\mathbf{r}) - E \right] \psi(\mathbf{k}, \mathbf{r}) = 0 \quad 2$$

Where μ is the reduced mass of the pair projectile and the target, \mathbf{r} is the separation of their center of mass and E is the energy in the center of the system. The time dependent Schrödinger equation for a free particle is

$$i\hbar \frac{\partial}{\partial t} \psi(\mathbf{r}, t) = -\frac{\hbar^2}{2m} \nabla^2 \psi(\mathbf{r}, t) \quad 3$$

Where the Hamiltonian is just the Newtonian kinetic energy

$$H = E_{total} = \frac{\mathbf{p}^2}{2m} = \frac{1}{2} m V^2 \quad 4$$

Schrödinger equation is a non-relativistic wave equation, meaning that it is based on classical approach assuming that the speed of light is not finite. This could not predict some experimental data accurately. This led to the thought of finding the relativistic solution to the wave equation. When considering particles traveling at the speed of light, modifications are required. These modifications use a time dependent wave equation known as the Klein-Gordon equation which is similar to the Schrödinger equation but includes a relativistic correction factor that takes into account the finite speed of light. It is derived from Dirac equation which is general relativistic wave equation used to describe the motion of a particle with spin. The relativistic relation derived from Lorentz invariant free particle energy-momentum equation is

$$E^2 = p^2 c^2 + m^2 c^4 \quad 5$$

Which is quantized by substituting $E = i\hbar \frac{\partial}{\partial t}$ and $\mathbf{p} = -i\hbar \nabla$ to get

$$-\hbar^2 \frac{\partial^2}{\partial t^2} \psi(\mathbf{x}, t) = (-\hbar^2 \nabla^2 c^2 + m^2 c^4) \psi(\mathbf{x}, t) \quad 6$$

Rearranging gives

$$\nabla^2 \psi(\mathbf{r}, t) - \frac{1}{c^2} \frac{\partial^2}{\partial t^2} \psi(\mathbf{r}, t) = \frac{m^2 c^2}{\hbar^2} \psi(\mathbf{r}, t) \quad 7$$

This is the Klein-Gordon equation. It is a relativistic equation for scalar field; a differential equation version of relativistic energy-momentum relation related to the Schrödinger equation. It is a continuous classical wave equation that can be quantized. The quantization process leads to quantum field whose quanta are spinless particles. The equation can be written in different forms i.e. by separating the space and time components or by combining them into a four-vector. It admits two values of negative and positive frequency for each wavenumber. By separating

out the positive and negative frequency parts, an equation describing a relativistic wave function is obtained. The Klein-Gordon equation for the time-independent case is

$$\left[\nabla^2 - \frac{m^2 c^2}{\hbar^2} \right] \psi(\mathbf{r}) = 0 \quad 8$$

Which is the Klein-Gordon equation for a free particle. It can be generalized to describe a field in some potential $V(\psi)$ as

$$\frac{1}{c^2} \frac{\partial^2}{\partial t^2} \psi(\mathbf{r}, t) - \nabla^2 \psi(\mathbf{r}, t) + \frac{m^2 c^2}{\hbar^2} \psi(\mathbf{r}, t) + \frac{\partial V}{\partial \psi} = 0 \quad 9$$

The equation is used for spinless particles. A solution to Klein-Gordon equation used for spin 1/2 particles is obtained by Dirac as

$$(i\gamma^\mu \partial_\mu - m) \psi(\mathbf{r}) = 0 \quad 10$$

The relativistic optical potential consists of two parts: one, $U_0(\mathbf{r})$, which transforms like the time like component of a Lorentz four-vector; the other $U_s(\mathbf{r})$ is a Lorentz scalar (Arnold and Clark 1979; Arnold et al. 1981). The Dirac equation with these potentials is

$$\left. \begin{aligned} [E - U_c(\mathbf{r}) - U_0(\mathbf{r}) - \beta[m + U_s(\mathbf{r})] \psi(\vec{\mathbf{r}})] &= -i\hbar c \vec{\alpha} \cdot \nabla \psi(\vec{\mathbf{r}}) \\ \text{i.e.} & \\ \{ \vec{\alpha} \cdot \vec{\mathbf{p}} + \beta[m + U_s(\mathbf{r})] + [U_0(\mathbf{r}) + U_c(\mathbf{r})] \} \psi(\vec{\mathbf{r}}) &= E \psi(\vec{\mathbf{r}}) \quad (\hbar = c = 1) \end{aligned} \right\} 11$$

where $U_c(\mathbf{r})$ is the Coulomb potential for charged nucleons determined from the empirical nuclear charge distribution, m is the nucleon mass, and E is the nucleon total energy. The complex potentials are written

$$\left. \begin{aligned} U_0(\mathbf{r}) &= V_o f_o(\mathbf{r}) + iW_o g_o(\mathbf{r}) \\ U_s(\mathbf{r}) &= V_s f_s(\mathbf{r}) + iW_s g_s(\mathbf{r}) \end{aligned} \right\} 12$$

The phenomenological Dirac optical potential (Cooper et al. 2009) has been used extensively to fit proton-nucleus elastic scattering data.

The elastic scattering of a particle on a potential is a function of energy. The real potential can be written as

$$V(\mathbf{r}, E) = V_o(\mathbf{r}) + \Delta V(\mathbf{r}, E) \quad 13$$

Here $V_o(\mathbf{r})$ is the energy dependent Hartree-Fock potential. The energy dependent part $\Delta V(\mathbf{r}, E)$ is the dynamical polarization potential which is the lost elastic flux that is accounted for by the imaginary potential $W(\mathbf{r}, E)$. The relationship between $\Delta V(\mathbf{r}, E)$ and $W(\mathbf{r}, E)$ can be described by a dispersion relation which the two must obey to satisfy the causality principle which states that a scattered wave cannot leave the target before the arrival of the incident wave. The dispersion relation is

$$\Delta V(\mathbf{r}, E) = \frac{P}{\pi} \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} \frac{W(\mathbf{r}, E')}{E' - E} dE' \quad 14$$

P is the principal value of the integral. The dispersive term is obtained analytically otherwise it is calculated by numerical integration (Morillon et al. 2024). It shows that

an energy-dependent imaginary potential $W(r, E)$ necessarily leads to a contribution $\Delta V(r, E)$ to the real potential. The unified description of the nuclear mean field in the dispersive optical model is accomplished by using a dispersion relation, which links the imaginary optical model parts to the corresponding dynamic real parts without requiring additional parameters. Furthermore, the dispersive constraint helps to reduce the ambiguities and the number of optical model parameters and also eliminates the need for energy-dependent geometry (Rui et al. 2013). Obviously, if the imaginary term is a surface one, the real term resulting from the dispersion relation will be a surface one as well in that order (Carlson 2000). The dispersive optical potential usually referred to as the Feshbach potential obeys a dispersion relation (Lépine-Szily et al. 1998). The dispersive here means not totally absorptive and not dispersive means that it is totally absorptive. Consideration of dispersion effects allows us to describe both bound and scattering states by the same nuclear mean field. The essence of the dispersion relation is to connect the real and the imaginary parts of the potential instead of treating them separately i.e. independent of each other. It relates scattering states and bound states on the same footing using a single potential. When composite particles are involved, a variety of phenomena is exhibited, these include elastic scattering, inelastic scattering, particle transfer, breakup, and fusion. These processes do not significantly affect each other therefore the two-body framework has to be extended by explicitly taking into account the interplay of the processes. Such formalism is referred to as the coupled-channels approach, and has been a standard method in low-energy nuclear reactions (Hagino et al. 2022). Phenomenological and microscopic potentials based on coupled-channel approach are formulated to fit into experimental results. These potentials are either relativistic or non-relativistic with dispersion or non-dispersive optical model potential based on coupled-channel approach (Capote et al. 2008; Quesada et al. 2013; Quesada et al. 2014). Distorted-Wave Born Approximation is used to describe weak interaction successfully where first-order perturbation treatment is correct approximation but when the interaction becomes stronger where the interactions are considered to infinite order, coupled-channel is used. That is when the interaction is stronger and the target is a collective nature (Tamura 1965).

Material and method

The cross-section calculation was done using Empire 3.2.3 (MALTA) Linux version installed on Fedora version 16 operating system 32-bit in an acer Laptop computer. was used for the calculation of the cross-section. The Empire code is a modular system of nuclear reaction codes written to facilitate the computational execution of various nuclear models. Empire 3.2.3 is an improved version which has benefitted from the experience gained in the previous editions. The goal is to obtain a powerful tool for modeling nuclear reactions that can be used in basic research as well as for the

generation of evaluated nuclear data files. There for, empire implements in a single system an extensive set of models that cover all the most important nuclear reaction mechanisms. These models provide a complete set of reaction channels and observables such as cross-sections that are of interest in nuclear applications. Such extensive calculations require a considerable number of input parameters. To provide them, empire incorporates a comprehensive library of model parameters, largely based on the IAEA Reference Input Parameter Library III (RIPL-3) project (Herman et al. 2015). Optical model input parameters such as optical model potential and the different calculation methods of the optical model calculation both for the single-channel and coupled-channels are included in the input file. The single-channel is the default option for nucleus with masses up to 220 otherwise coupled-channels are used. Different values are used to select the calculation methods as follows:

The value 0 is used for spherical optical model. In this option, the direct cross-sections are exact but spherical transmission coefficients are used for subsequent pre-equilibrium and Hauser-Feshbach calculations in the whole energy grid (Herman et al. 2015). These results are re-normalized at the transmission coefficient level by taking into account direct component. The total, elastic, absorption and the inelastic cross-sections are taken from the coupled-channel calculations if a coupled-channel optical model potential is being used otherwise only inelastic cross-sections are accepted.

The value 1 is used to calculate coupled-channel transmission coefficients for the incident channel in addition to Distorted-Wave Born Approximation uncoupled (Herman et al. 2015). In this optical model cross-section calculation mechanism, the population of collective levels in the incident channel is calculated using the coupled-channels model for coupled levels and Distorted-Wave Born Approximation method for uncoupled discrete levels and levels embedded in the continuum.

The value 2 is used for coupled-channel transmission coefficients for the incident and outgoing channel in addition to Distorted-Wave Born Approximation uncoupled (Herman et al. 2015). In this optical model mechanism, the population of collective levels both in the incident and outgoing channels is calculated using the coupled-channels model for coupled levels and Distorted-Wave Born Approximation method for uncoupled discrete levels and levels embedded in the continuum. Importantly, the coupled-channel is used consistently, considering the ground state and the coupled levels, to calculate all necessary transmission coefficients for subsequent pre-equilibrium and Hauser-Feshbach calculations. These coupled-channel transmission coefficients define absorption cross-section that is available for the pre-equilibrium and Hauser-Feshbach decay. The absorption cross-section sums up with the direct cross-sections to collective levels to the reaction cross-section. This option is an exact option that considers flux decrease due to the collective excitations at the level of transmission coefficient. It is a recommended option for accurate calculations whenever an appropriate

coupled-channels model potential is available though it takes time in the calculation.

The value 3 is used for Distorted-Wave Born Approximation calculation for all collective levels (Herman et al. 2015). This is an optical model cross-section calculation where the population of discrete collective levels in the inelastic scattering is calculated using the Distorted-Wave Born Approximation method providing approximate direct cross-sections. The spherical transmission coefficients are used for the whole energy grid in subsequent pre-equilibrium and Hauser-Feshbach calculations. These results are re-normalized at the transmission coefficient level by taking into account Distorted-Wave Born Approximation calculated direct component.

To determine the effect of the optical model on the production cross-section, the coupled-channel optical models 1, 2 and 3 were used instead of the single-channel because the target Thorium-232 has a massive nucleus capable of deformation. The optical models' configurations were designated by D1, D2 and D3 respectively. Empire uses ECIS and OPTMAN codes to implement the coupled-channel and the Distorted-Wave Born Approximation for the optical model calculations. The OPTMAN can be invoked by the Empire for D1 and D2 methods of calculation when optical model potentials that use either soft-rotor for spherical nuclei, or rigid-rotor or deformed vibrational rotational model for deformed nuclei are being used (Herman et al. 2015). The different optical model potentials with proton incident particles were used as the RIPL optical model potentials to test the effect of dispersive and relative potential, non-dispersive and relative potential, and the non-dispersive and non-relativistic potentials. The optical model potentials were all taken from the Reference Input Parameter Library (RIPL) as contained in Empire 3.2.3. Table 1 contains the optical model potentials used for the investigation i.e. the optical model potentials with RIPL number 4303, 5600 and 5408 were used for the investigation. They are global, coupled-channels rigid rotor with energy range of 0–200 MeV that are non-dispersive and non-relativistic, non-dispersive and relativistic, and dispersive and relativistic respectively.

To verify the effects of optical models and the dispersive and relativistic potentials to the cross-section calculations, recoils were not calculated. The pre-equilibrium contribution was made by the combination of the Hybrid Monte-Carlo Simulation (HMS) phenomenological pre-equilibrium and the exciton model with mean free path of 3.0. The HFB accounted for the emitted neutrons and protons in both discrete and continuum levels while the exciton model accounted for the gamma emission at the pre-equilibrium level. This model was used because

of its capability to account for multiple emission (Herman et al. 2005). For the Hauser-Feshbach contribution, the default Enhanced Generalized Superfluid level density model was used. The Level Density parameter in ^{232}Th was multiplied by 3.05. The ^{225}Ac possible production cross-section route through $^{232}\text{Th}(p,x)^{225}\text{Ac}$ reaction were calculated with proton energy from 0 to 200 MeV. The possible routes are $^{232}\text{Th}(p,6n2p)^{225}\text{Ac}$, $^{232}\text{Th}(p,6n-2p)^{225}\text{Ac}$, $^{232}\text{Th}(p,5n\text{He-3})^{225}\text{Ac}$, $^{232}\text{Th}(p,4npt)^{225}\text{Ac}$ and $^{232}\text{Th}(p,4n\alpha)^{225}\text{Ac}$. The result obtained were compared with the measured data obtained from the experimental nuclear reaction data EXchange FORmat (EXFOR) library contained in the nuclear data section of the IAEA. The method of retrieval is contained in our previous work (Longmena et al. 2023).

Result and discussion

The result of the calculation of the production cross-section using the various optical model configurations D1, D2 and D3 to determine the best configuration to be used for the calculation of the production cross-section. The result of the investigation of the optical model relativistic and dispersive potentials is also presented in this section. The calculated production cross-section data are plotted along the experimental production cross-sections and presented in the respective figures below. The results are discussed accordingly. In the calculation, there were missing spin/parity for ^{224}Ac at different levels of excited state and 0.00 1 was assigned to it by the code. The ground-state of ^{226}Pa has no assigned spin/parity. The branching ratios and the conversion coefficients for different levels in ^{233}Pa , ^{232}Th and ^{229}Ac were missing.

Fig. 2 is the comparison of the calculated cross-section base on $^{232}\text{Th}(p,6n2p)^{225}\text{Ac}$ reaction. It shows that the three configurations (D1, D2 and D3) reach the same maximum intensity of approximately 19 mb at the 30 MeV mark. It does not show significant disparity among the models in the low-energy region. There is very small disparity between the three models across most of the energy spectrum. D2 and D3 models are nearly identical throughout the 20–200 MeV energy range. They follow the same trajectory, including the peak at 30 MeV and the subsequent decline. The model D1 shows the most visible divergence, particularly between 70 and 135 MeV, where its cross-section calculation is slightly higher than that of D2 and D3 which tend towards the experimental data. Above 135 MeV, the three models converge completely, dropping to a consistent low cross-section between 1 and 2 mb. This is attributed to the failure of the Hauser-Feshbach and the pre-equilibrium models.

Table 1. The optical model potentials

RIPL No.	Incident Particle	Model Type	Dispersive	Relativistic	Z-Range	A-Range	E-Range (MeV)	References
4303	P	CC rigid	no	no	90–92	228–234	.0–200.0	Ignatyuk et al. (2002)
5600	p	CC rigid	no	yes	9–94	232–242	.0–200.0	Soukhovitskii et al. (2005)
5408	p	CC rigid	yes	yes	90–97	228–249	.0–200.0	Capote et al. (2008)

Figure 2. Comparison of optical model configurations calculation of $^{232}\text{Th}(p,6n2p)^{225}\text{Ac}$ reaction cross-sections.

There is significant scattering among the experimental datasets, which is common in thorium spallation studies: Steyn et al. (2021) and Ermolaev et al. (2012) show good agreement in the 40–70 MeV range, defining a clear hump that the models attempt to follow. Older data like Gauvin (1963) are significantly lower than modern measurements, highlighting the evolution of measurement precision over the decades. Moreover, the one point measured by Lefort et al. (1961) is the only older data measured at high energy region.

Similarly, in the comparison of the models based on the cross-section of $^{232}\text{Th}(p,4n\alpha)^{225}\text{Ac}$ reaction presented in Fig. 3, the level of disparity between the models is extremely low across the entire energy range. D2 and D3 models are nearly indistinguishable, following an almost identical trajectory from 20 to 200 MeV. Model D1 shows the most deviation, appearing as a slightly higher line compared to D2 and D3 in the energy region between 70 and 90 MeV. Above 90 MeV the deviations are negligible dropping to a consistent low-value below 2 mb. Below 70 MeV, the three models converge completely with

Figure 3. Comparison of optical model configurations calculation of $^{232}\text{Th}(p,4n\alpha)^{225}\text{Ac}$ reaction cross-sections.

low-energy peak cross-section of 19 mb around 30 MeV.

From both Figs 2, 3, the three models predict a sharp reaction peak around 30 MeV much earlier than observed in modern experimental datasets like Steyn et al. (2021) and Ermolaev et al. (2012), which show the reaction threshold of 40 MeV. From 90 MeV to 200 MeV, the models capture the oscillatory nature of the cross-section but generally under-predict the experimental values at the Hauser-Feshbach and the

pre-equilibrium models significant contribution region. The three model variations are almost indistinguishable across most of the energy range, suggesting that the choice between uncoupled and fully collective DWBA treatments in these specific EMPIRE configurations D1, D2, and D3 have a negligible impact on this specific isotope’s production cross-section in EMPIRE. Also, adding coupled-channel transmission coefficients for the outgoing channel does not significantly alter the predicted cross-sections. Specifically, the models are likely favouring the emission of other particles or fission over the channels been studied as energy increases. However, D1 model tend to diverge towards the experimental data more than D2 and D3 models suggesting that D1 which is coupled channel transmission coefficients for the incident channel and spherical by distorted wave born approximation uncoupled should be used for further calculations.

Having determined the optical model calculation method, the different optical model potentials of non-dispersive and non-relativistic (Non-Disp. & Non-Rel.), non-dispersive and relativistic (Non-Disp. & Rel.), and dispersive and relativistic (Disp. & Rel.) of the optical model parameters were investigated and the results presented in Figs 4–8. Fig. 4 shows the comparison of the relativistic and dispersive potentials base on $^{232}\text{Th}(p,6n2p)^{225}\text{Ac}$ reaction cross-section. This is the channel where its emissions are all nucleons of 2 protons and 6 neutrons. The figure shows all the models significantly over-predicting the experimental cross-section between 20 and 40 MeV, reaching a peak near 20 mb, whereas experimental data (e.g., Ermolaev et al. 2012) suggest much lower values.

Figure 4. Comparison of the effect of optical potentials in the calculations of $^{232}\text{Th}(p,6n2p)^{225}\text{Ac}$ reaction cross-sections.

The model with Non-Dispersive & Non-Relativistic effect consistently yields the highest cross-section values across the entire energy range. It is slightly closer to the experimental data in the 50–90 MeV range but contributes most to the over-prediction at the 30 MeV peak. This shows that introducing relativistic effects slightly lowers the calculated cross-section compared to the non-relativistic version. This adjustment brings the model marginally closer to the lower-bound experimental points (like Weidner et al. 2012) between 50 and 95 MeV. The model with Dispersive & Relativistic effect is the most complex model, accounting for the dispersion relation and relativistic effects. In this plot, it produces the lowest cross-section

values of the three. While this helps mitigate the over-prediction at 30 MeV, it results in the greatest divergence from the experimental data at energies above 100 MeV.

The models suggest the reaction becomes significant much earlier (25 MeV) than the experimental consensus, which shows a more gradual rise starting around 40–50 MeV. The three lines are most distinct between 40 and 100 MeV. The Non-Dispersive & Non-Relativistic potentials appears to predict the experimental peaks (like those from Steyn et al. near 55 MeV) better, while the Dispersive & Relativistic model is more conservative. The fact that all models drop off after 100 MeV suggests that the chosen optical model potentials or the level density parameters used in these calculations may not be accounting for high-energy pre-equilibrium effects or specific spallation-like mechanisms that dominate at higher incident proton energies.

In the prediction of emission of cluster of deuterons among the nucleons in $^{232}\text{Th}(p,5\text{ndp})^{225}\text{Ac}$ reaction, (Fig. 5), just as observed in the previous analysis of $^{232}\text{Th}(p,6\text{n}2\text{p})^{225}\text{Ac}$, the theoretical calculations for the (p, 5ndp) component generally exhibit a sharp theoretical peak near 30 MeV. Between 50 and 90 MeV, the models show a structured cross-section that attempts to follow the fluctuations in the data. Here, the model with Non-Disp. & Non-Rel. yields the highest excitation function. In reactions involving deuteron emission, this model often over-predicts the probability because it lacks the damping effects provided by relativistic kinematics or dispersive corrections to the potential depth. In the model with Non-Disp. & Rel. potential, the relativistic correction slightly reduces the cross-section. This is particularly noticeable in the 40–100 MeV range, where the green line sits consistently below the purple line, marginally improving the fit to Steyn et al. (2021) data points. Similar to the (p,6n2p) channels, the model with Disp. & Rel. potential is the most conservative of the three. By using a dispersive optical model potential (DOMP), the imaginary part of the potential is linked to the real part via dispersion relations. This typically results in a lower peak cross-section, which is the closest theoretical representation to the lower-bound experimental data in the mid-energy region.

Figure 5. Comparison of the effect of optical potentials in the calculations of $^{232}\text{Th}(p,5\text{ndp})^{225}\text{Ac}$ reaction cross-sections.

The (p, 5ndp) channel involves the emission of a composite particle (d). The models likely treat this via a combination of pre-equilibrium emission and evaporation. The under-prediction at high energies could suggest the pre-equilibrium pick-up/knock-out components for deuterons might be under-parameterized.

Similar results are obtained for the production channels where Helium-3 is emitted among the nucleons in $^{232}\text{Th}(p,5\text{nHe-3})^{225}\text{Ac}$ reaction (Fig. 6).

Figure 6. Comparison of the effect of optical potentials in the calculations of $^{232}\text{Th}(p,5\text{n}^3\text{He})^{225}\text{Ac}$ reaction cross-sections.

The theoretical curves for the (p, 5n³He) channel follow the same systematic behaviour as the previously discussed (p, 6n2p) and (p, 5ndp) channels. All models predict a sharp excitation peak near 30 MeV (about 20 mb) that is entirely absent in the experimental data Fig. 6). The models attempt to simulate the fluctuations in experimental data, showing a local peak near 85 MeV (about 6 mb). This moderately aligns with data points from Grisworld et al., Weidner et al. and Zhuikov et al. in that energy.

The model with Non-Disp. & Non-Rel. parameters yields the highest cross-section values. Without relativistic or dispersive corrections, the model assumes a more transparent nucleus with higher emission probabilities for cluster particles like ³He. In the model with Non-Disp. & Rel. parameters, the inclusion of relativistic kinematics slightly reduces the predicted yields compared to the non-relativistic case. This provides a marginally better fit to the lower experimental bounds seen around 70–80 MeV. The Disp. & Rel. generally provides the lowest and most constrained cross-section. By linking the real and imaginary parts of the optical potential through dispersion relations, it accounts for the energy dependence of the potential depth more rigorously, though it still suffers from the same high-energy under-prediction.

The three models are nearly identical at very high and very low energies but show visible divergence in the 40–100 MeV region. The Non-Dispersive & Non-Relativistic model remains the most optimistic regarding production yields, while the Dispersive & Relativistic model is the most physically conservative.

In the prediction of $^{232}\text{Th}(p,4\text{npt})^{225}\text{Ac}$ reaction (Fig. 7), the model with Non-Disp. & Non-Rel. po-

tential consistently predicts the highest cross-section across the entire energy range. In the model with Non-Disp. & Rel. potential, the inclusion of relativistic kinematics results in a slight reduction of the cross-section magnitude compared to the non-relativistic case. This brings the mid-energy calculations slightly closer to the lower data points. The model with Disp. & Rel. potential provides the most conservative (lowest) values. The use of a dispersive optical model potential (DOMP) constrains the excitation function, which helps reduce the low-energy over-prediction but contributes to the under-prediction at higher energies. In the region between 40 MeV and 70 MeV, the models are most sensitive to the specific potential used. The Non-Dispersive & Non-Relativistic potential appears to track the shape of the Steyn et al. data more closely in terms of trend, even if the absolute magnitude remains shifted.

Figure 7. Comparison of the effect of optical potentials in the calculations of $^{232}\text{Th}(p,4npt)^{225}\text{Ac}$ reaction cross-sections.

In the comparison of the effect of the relativistic and dispersive optical potentials on $^{232}\text{Th}(p,4n\alpha)^{225}\text{Ac}$ reaction cross-sections (Fig. 8), in the 50–90 MeV range, the models show some structure, attempting to follow the fluctuations in the experimental data, with a small local peak near 85 MeV. The model with Non-Disp. & Non-Rel. potential predicts the highest cross-section values. This model typically provides the most optimum production yields but shows the greatest deviation from the experimental threshold. In the model with Non-Disp. & Rel. potential, the inclusion of relativistic kinematics leads to a slight reduction in the calculated cross-section compared to the non-relativistic version, marginally improving the fit to lower-bound experimental points. As seen above, the model with Disp. & Rel. potential generally provides the most conservative (lowest) values. The use of a dispersive optical model potential (DOMP) constrains the excitation function, which helps mitigate the over-prediction at 30 MeV but increases the gap at higher energies. The theoretical output for the $(p, 4n\alpha)$ reaction is identical in shape to the $(p, 6n2p)$ and $(p, 5ndp)$ channels, indicating that the current optical model parameters treat these different $A = 225$ isobaric contributors with similar probability distributions.

Figure 8. Comparison of the effect of optical potentials in the calculations of $^{232}\text{Th}(p,4n\alpha)^{225}\text{Ac}$ reaction cross-sections.

The comparative analysis of the various reaction channels for ^{225}Ac production reveals a consistent performance pattern across the theoretical models, alongside distinct physical challenges for each. All five reaction channels — $(p, 6n2p)$, $(p, 5ndp)$, $(p, 5n^3\text{He})$, $(p, 4npt)$, and $(p, 4n\alpha)$ — share a fundamental theoretical behaviour in the calculations. Every model predicts a dominant, non-physical peak around 30 MeV (about 20 mb). This is due to a failure in the compound nucleus evaporation parameters which miscalculate the competition between these channels at low energies. All models collapse to a baseline below 5 mb after 100 MeV. In contrast, experimental data (e.g., Weidner et al. 2012; Griswold et al. 2016) show cross-section rising toward 20 mb as spallation and pre-equilibrium mechanisms dominate. The channels involving cluster emission (e.g., ^3He , t , α) show slightly more model divergence in the 40–90 MeV range, reflecting the difficulty of modeling complex particle pick-up or knock-out processes.

The combination of dispersive and relativistic effects (Disp. & Rel.) tracks almost perfectly with the Non-Disp. & Rel. model. This suggests that the dispersive component of the optical model potential (OMP) provides minimal correction for this specific interaction compared to the relativistic adjustment.

Conclusion

From the discussion and the observation above, all three configurations predict a significant reaction peak at 30 MeV. This shows threshold that is higher than simple (p, xn) reactions. The presence of this peak in the models indicates a potential issue with how the models handle the competition between different $A = 225$ isobaric contributors at low energy.

All three theoretical curves drop to below 2 mb above 110 MeV. The collapse of the models after 110 MeV highlights a systemic gap in how these optical models handle the transition from compound nucleus evaporation to direct spallation/multi-particle emission regimes. These can be attributed to the failure of the Hauser-Feshbach models (the default Enhance Generalised Superfluid model level density) and the pre-equilibrium models (the combination

of the HMS and the exciton pre-equilibrium models) to effectively replicate the experimental data.

Though the different optical models' configurations is to provide physical realities of the nuclear reactions, it was observed that they do not have any significant variant effects on the calculation of the cross-section of Thorium production of ^{225}Ac by proton bombardment of Thorium within energy range from threshold to 200 MeV.

The relativistic and the dispersive potentials did not show significant effect in the calculations. The optical model with non-dispersive and non-relativistic potentials produces highest yield across the energy range of 20–200 MeV. It tends to move towards the experimental data at mid-energy and high energy regions but contributed most in the overestimation of the low energy peak. Thus, the Non-Dispersive & Non-Relativistic model remains the most optimistic regarding production yields, while the Dispersive & Relativistic model is the most physically conservative.

This shows that any of the models can be used for the calculation of the cross-sections. Though based on the physical accuracy and the alignment with the lower bounds of experimental data, the model with Dispersive & Relativistic (Disp. & Rel.) potentials has more advantage and the most recommended for further development. It utilizes

the Dispersive Optical Model (DOM), which uses dispersion relations to link the real and imaginary parts of the potential. This provides a more consistent treatment of nuclear structure and reaction dynamics compared to local, non-dispersive potentials. By linking the real and imaginary parts of the potential via dispersion relations, it accounts for the energy dependence of the potential depth and surface absorption more accurately. It consistently provides the most conservative (lowest) cross-section values. While it still overestimates the 30 MeV peak, its magnitude is lower than the other models, making it closer to the experimental reality in that region.

Even though this study did not show much deviation between the models, proton irradiation of heavy targets like Thorium at energies reaching 200 MeV and beyond requires relativistic kinematics to correctly simulate the scattering wavefunctions and non-elastic cross-sections.

Including relativistic effects is critical for proton energies above 100 MeV to correctly describe the scattering wavefunctions and the absorption cross-section. It offers the best baseline for addressing the high-energy under-prediction. Since it is already the most theoretically rigorous, adjusting its pre-equilibrium parameters or adding a spallation component would yield a more reliable fit than adjusting the mathematically simpler models.

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Additional information

Conflict of interest

The authors have declared that no competing interests exist.

Ethical statement

No ethical statement was reported.

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Data availability

All of the data that support the findings of this study are available in the main text.
